

Control Strategies in Multigroup Models: The Case of the Star Network Topology

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Abstract In this paper, we propose control strategies for multigroup epidemic models. We use compartmental *SIRS* models to study the dynamics of n host groups sharing the same source of infection in addition to the transmission among members of the same group. In particular, we consider a model for infectious diseases with free-living pathogens in the environment and a metapopulation model with a central patch. We give the detailed derivation of the target reproduction number under three public health interventions and provide the corresponding biological insights. Moreover, using the next-generation approach, we calculate the basic reproduction numbers associated with subsystems of our models and determine algebraic connections to the target reproduction number of the complete model. The analysis presented here illustrates that understanding the topological structure of the infection process and partitioning it in simple cycles is useful to design and evaluate control strategies.

Keywords Control strategies · Target reproduction number · Multigroup model · Star Network · Basic reproduction number.

1 Introduction

An omnipresent quantity in the modeling of infectious diseases is the basic reproduction number \mathcal{R}_0 (Heesterbeek, 2002). The value of \mathcal{R}_0 not only is an indicator of the severity of an epidemic, it is also a powerful tool to estimate

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the control effort needed to eradicate a disease when treating homogeneous populations. In fact, for homogeneous populations, it is known (Keeling et al., 2013) that an infection can be eliminated provided that a proportion of individuals greater than $1-1/\mathcal{R}_0$ have been afforded lifelong protection.

However, for a large number of infectious diseases the host population is not homogeneous (Roberts and Heesterbeek, 2003). Furthermore, in real situations, there are multiple constraints (economic and geographical considerations for example) that may significantly affect the design of control policies. Therefore, it is not uncommon that control strategies are not aimed at all host individuals; instead, they treat a particular group of individuals or interactions between them.

When designing control measures that target specific types of individuals in heterogeneous populations, the concept of the target reproduction number proposed in (Shuai et al., 2013) arises naturally to quantify the effort needed to control epidemic outbreaks. The basic idea behind the method of Shuai et al. (Shuai et al., 2015) is that it is possible to reduce the value of \mathcal{R}_0 by controlling a specific set S of entries of the next-generation matrix $\mathbf{K} = [k_{ij}]$. Let \mathbf{K}_S be the target matrix corresponding to the target set S defined by $[\mathbf{K}_S]_{ij} = k_{ij}$ if $(i, j) \in S$ and 0, otherwise. The target reproduction number \mathcal{T}_S for the target set S is defined as the spectral radius of the matrix $\mathbf{K}_S \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_S)^{-1}$, provided that $\rho(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_S) < 1$, where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix and ρ denotes the spectral radius. This last condition had been called the controllability condition (Knipf, 2016), since whenever $\rho(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_S) > 1$ the disease cannot be eradicated by targeting only S (Shuai et al., 2013). However, since the term controllability evokes formal control theory, we will not use this terminology.

Analogously to \mathcal{R}_0 , the target reproduction number has the property that if a proportion bigger than $1 - 1/\mathcal{T}_S$ of the S entries in \mathbf{K} can be reduced, then the disease can be eradicated. Moreover, when the next-generation matrix is irreducible then $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$ if and only if $\mathcal{T}_S < 1$ for a general target set S , as long as the target reproduction number is well defined.

On the other hand, for many diseases the structure of the infection process can be subdivided as a combination of different cycles of infection (Olmos et al., 2015) and it is logical to speculate if there is a relationship between the topological structure of the cycles of infection and the optimal design of public health interventions. Therefore, we propose to examine and control the local dynamics of an infection with a heterogeneous host population to prevent a major outbreak at the global level. In particular, our focus will be models with multiple host types whose infection process follows the star network topology (Edwards et al., 2010) i.e. models with a common source of infection for all the groups but not direct transmission between them.

Using these ideas, in this paper we establish connections among the target reproduction number for the whole model and \mathcal{R}_0 's of sub-models that facilitate the design and evaluation of control strategies. In section 2, we illustrate our method with an epidemiological model for leptospirosis in humans and animals. Different control strategies are proposed and the target reproduction number is computed in each case. General models with n hosts types

are studied in section 3. In particular, we consider a compartmental model for infections with free-living pathogens in the environment and a metapopulation model with a central patch. In the last section, we summarize and interpret our results.

2 Leptospirosis as an example of an environmentally-driven disease

Leptospirosis is a bacterial disease caused by certain members of the genus *Leptospira*. Except for Antarctica, leptospirosis is present in all continents (Adler and de la Peña Moctezuma, 2010) with more than 500,000 cases per year reported globally (Ullmann and Langoni, 2011). Although rodents have been recognized as the most important reservoirs of leptospiral infection; humans, domestic pets, cattle and almost every mammal can also contract this infection (Evangelista and Coburn, 2010).

Environmental conditions play an important role in the transmission of leptospirosis. In fact, leptospires can survive in moist soil and fresh water for a few weeks up to several months (Ko et al., 1999). Moreover, both humans and animals become infected with leptospires through close contact with water, food, or soil contaminated mainly with the urine of reservoir animals (Ganoza et al., 2006). Human to human transmission is also possible by sexual intercourse, transplacentally from mother to fetus and via breast milk to a child. Urine from a patient suffering from leptospirosis should be considered infectious (Terpstra, 2003).

Several mathematical models have been proposed to study the transmission of leptospirosis in a population over time. In (Holt et al., 2006) the authors proposed a model to study the spread and maintenance of leptospirosis in rodents. One of the first compartmental models for leptospirosis that considered both human and animals was proposed in (Triampo et al., 2007). In their work, they proposed a deterministic *SIRS* (susceptible-infectious-recovered-susceptible) model and considered real data of leptospirosis in Thailand. Recently, in (Baca-Carrasco et al., 2015) an epidemiological model that included explicitly a variable for the leptospires in the environment was proposed. This model considers the indirect infections caused by the bacteria present in the environment; however, it did not include possible direct transmissions between humans.

Here we present a two-group epidemiological *SIRS* model for the dynamics of leptospiral infection in humans and animals. Given the importance of the indirect infections caused by contact with a contaminated environment, we consider an equation for the free-living leptospira in the environment as in (Baca-Carrasco et al., 2015) but we also allow direct transmissions among humans. To derive our model, let $S_i(t)$, $I_i(t)$ and $R_i(t)$ denote the number of susceptible, infectious and recovered individuals of host type $i \in \{1, 2\}$ at time t , with $i = 1$ representing humans and $i = 2$ representing animals. Therefore the total population size of host type i at time t is given by $N_i(t) =$

$S_i(t) + I_i(t) + R_i(t)$ for $i \in \{1, 2\}$. The variable $P(t)$ represent the amount of leptospira present in the environment.

We assume that individuals enter to the population as susceptibles at a constant rate Λ_i , and die at a per capita death rate μ_i , $i = 1, 2$. No additional death due to the disease is considered. Susceptible humans can be infected by direct (sexual) contact with other humans at a rate β_{11} and indirectly via the external environment at a rate β_{1p} . New infections in animals are also due to direct contact with infected animals at a rate β_{22} and through indirect exposure with a contaminated environment at a rate β_{2p} . Infectious individuals of host type $i \in \{1, 2\}$ recover at a constant rate γ_i proportional to the size of their class and the loss of immunity occurs at an average time of $1/\nu_i$. The presence of leptospira in the environment increases due to the shedding of infected humans and animals at rates c_1 and c_2 , respectively. The bacteria survive in the environment for a mean time of $1/\mu_p$.

Under these hypotheses, our model is given by the following system of differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{S}_i &= \Lambda_i - (\beta_{ii}I_i/N_i + \beta_{ip}P)S_i - \mu_i S_i + \nu_i R_i, \\ \dot{I}_i &= (\beta_{ii}I_i/N_i + \beta_{ip}P)S_i - (\mu_i + \gamma_i)I_i, \quad i \in \{1, 2\} \\ \dot{R}_i &= \gamma_i I_i - (\nu_i + \mu_i)R_i, \\ \dot{P} &= c_1 I_1 + c_2 I_2 - \mu_p P.\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

All the parameters are considered nonnegative. Note that we assumed mass action incidence for the indirect (environment-to-host) transmission and standard incidence for the direct (host-to-host) transmission.

It is easy to see that the total population size for any host type is asymptotically constant since

$$\dot{N}_i = \Lambda_i - \mu_i N_i, \quad i \in \{1, 2\}.$$

The unique disease free equilibrium of system (1) is given by

$$\varepsilon_0 = (N_1^*, 0, 0, N_2^*, 0, 0, 0)\tag{2}$$

with $N_i^* = \Lambda_i/\mu_i$ for $i \in \{1, 2\}$.

Disregarding the infections caused by the contaminated environment it is easy to calculate the basic reproduction number associated with the direct transmission of the disease for any host type,

$$\mathcal{R}_i = \frac{\beta_{ii}}{\mu_i + \gamma_i}, \quad i \in \{1, 2\}\tag{3}$$

and \mathcal{R}_i gives the average number of secondary infectious corresponding to the direct transmission cycle for the i^{th} host-type. The dynamics of the infection process for system (1) is shown in Fig. 1.

As many examples in the literature show (Baca-Carrasco and Velasco-Hernández, 2016; Chen et al., 2009; Martcheva, 2015; Olmos et al., 2015), the

Fig. 1: Topological structure of the infection process for model (1). In this case, there are two infection cycles, for both, the indirect transmission (\mathcal{R}_{1p} and \mathcal{R}_{2p}) and the direct transmission (\mathcal{R}_1 and \mathcal{R}_2).

expressions for \mathcal{R}_0 in multigroup models can be very complex, so it would be very useful when evaluating public health interventions to have an expression of \mathcal{R}_0 in terms of \mathcal{R}_0 's of sub-models of the whole system. This will allow the design of local strategies such as control of specific types of individuals or even interactions between them to control the disease at the global level. As previously mentioned, when targeting specific types of individuals or interactions it is easier to work with the target reproduction number \mathcal{T}_S than with \mathcal{R}_0 . Moreover, we know \mathcal{T}_S and \mathcal{R}_0 are directly related. In fact, if the next-generation matrix $\mathbf{K} = [k_{ij}]$ is irreducible then $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$ if and only if $\mathcal{T}_S < 1$ when the target reproduction number is well defined for the target set S (Shuai et al., 2013, 2015).

In general terms, to compute the next-generation matrix it is necessary to determine the subsystem that describes the production of new infections and changes in state among infected individuals. The Jacobian matrix \mathbf{J} corresponding to the linearization of this subsystem at the infection-free equilibrium is decomposed as $\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{V}$. The matrix \mathbf{F} is the transmission part, describing the production of new infections, and \mathbf{V} describes changes in status, such as recovery or death (Knipl, 2016; Martcheva, 2015; Van den Driessche and Watmough, 2002).

However, different interpretations of the disease process can lead to different decompositions into matrices \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{V} . Consequently, different next-generation matrices can be obtained for a compartmental model. This problem is of particular relevance for infections that can be caused by contact with a contaminated environment since the role of the environment can be interpreted in multiple ways (Bani-Yaghoub et al., 2012). In this work, we assume that the environment acts as a reservoir of the infection. Therefore, the pathogen shedding by infectious hosts are placed in the matrix \mathbf{F} .

These assumptions give the following matrices \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{V} for model (1), computed at the disease-free equilibrium (2):

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_{11} & 0 & \beta_{1p}N_1^* \\ 0 & \beta_{22} & \beta_{2p}N_2^* \\ c_1 & c_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{V} = \begin{pmatrix} \mu_1 + \gamma_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_2 + \gamma_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mu_p \end{pmatrix}$$

The product \mathbf{FV}^{-1} gives the following next-generation matrix

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{R}_1 & 0 & \frac{\beta_{1p}N_1^*}{\mu_p} \\ 0 & \mathcal{R}_2 & \frac{\beta_{2p}N_2^*}{\mu_p} \\ \frac{c_1}{\mu_1 + \gamma_1} & \frac{c_2}{\mu_2 + \gamma_2} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

which is clearly an irreducible matrix. Using (4) it is not difficult to show that the basic reproduction numbers for the indirect transmission cycle (see figure 1) are given by the following formula

$$\mathcal{R}_{ip} = \sqrt{\frac{c_i \beta_{ip} N_i^*}{\mu_p (\mu_i + \gamma_i)}}, \quad i \in \{1, 2\}. \quad (5)$$

Indeed, the characteristic polynomial of the next-generation matrix (4) is

$$\begin{aligned} P(\lambda) = & \lambda^3 - (\mathcal{R}_1 + \mathcal{R}_2) \lambda^2 + \left(\mathcal{R}_1 \mathcal{R}_2 - \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{c_i \beta_{ip} N_i^*}{\mu_p (\mu_i + \gamma_i)} \right) \lambda \\ & + \left((\mathcal{R}_1 + \mathcal{R}_2) \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{c_i \beta_{ip} N_i^*}{\mu_p (\mu_i + \gamma_i)} - \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{c_i \beta_{ip} N_i^* \mathcal{R}_i}{\mu_p (\mu_i + \gamma_i)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

If we set the reproduction numbers associated with the direct transmission of the disease equal to zero, we get

$$\tilde{P}(\lambda) = \lambda^3 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{c_i \beta_{ip} N_i^*}{\mu_p (\mu_i + \gamma_i)} \right) \lambda.$$

In order to obtain, for example, \mathcal{R}_{1p} we only need to compute the root of maximum modulus of $\tilde{P}(\lambda)$ when the transmission parameters between host type 2 and the contaminated environment are zero i.e. $\beta_{2p} = c_2 = 0$. Hence, \mathcal{R}_{ip} satisfies (5).

The expression for the \mathcal{R}_0 of the complete model is quite complicated and we are not going to show it here. Instead, we are going to work with the target reproduction number since we know that reducing this quantity below 1 ensures the elimination of the disease, see Theorem 1 below.

A wide variety of public health interventions can be of help to reduce the spread of leptospirosis. We analyze some of them in the following section.

2.1 Control strategies in the two-group model for leptospirosis

Leptospirosis can be considered an environmentally-driven disease because of the important role of environmental conditions in the transmission of the disease. Different control strategies could be applied to reduce the prevalence of environmentally-driven diseases in general and leptospirosis in particular.

(A) *Minimizing exposures to environmental risk factors.* The vast majority of human and animal infections with leptospira arise from contact with contaminated water (Terpstra, 2003). Therefore, one effective way to minimize the chances of infection is to avoid contact with contaminated water. In humans, factors related to occupational and recreational activities can represent an increased risk of infection. For example, farmers may be exposed to water contaminated by the urine of rodents or other animals when irrigating fields (Terpstra, 2003). Hence, where appropriate, protective clothing should be worn to reduce the risk of infection.

When preventive measures aim to reduce exposure to environmental risk factors, the target set is $S = \{(1, 3), (2, 3)\}$. Following the notation in (Shuai et al., 2013) the target matrix \mathbf{K}_S is defined by,

$$[\mathbf{K}_S]_{ij} = \begin{cases} k_{ij}, & \text{if } (i, j) \in S \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

hence the condition $\rho(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_S) < 1$ becomes

$$\max\{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2\} < 1. \quad (6)$$

This condition is logical since we cannot expect to eradicate a disease by just reducing the indirect infections caused by environmental factors when any of the basic reproduction numbers associated to the host-to-host transmission cycle has a value above 1. Provided that the condition (6) is fulfilled, the target reproduction number is defined as the spectral radius of the matrix $\mathbf{K}_S \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_S)^{-1}$ given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} & \frac{c_2 \beta_{1p} N_1^*}{\mu_p (\mu_2 + \gamma_2) (1 - \mathcal{R}_2)} & \frac{\beta_{1p} N_1^*}{\mu_p} \\ \frac{c_1 \beta_{2p} N_2^*}{\mu_p (\mu_1 + \gamma_1) (1 - \mathcal{R}_1)} & \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2} & \frac{\beta_{2p} N_2^*}{\mu_p} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Therefore

$$\mathcal{T}_S = \frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2}. \quad (7)$$

Hence, \mathcal{T}_S is an increasing function of each of the local basic reproduction numbers when it is well defined.

(B) *Reducing the shedding rate.* The reduction of certain animal reservoirs such as rodents, immunization of dogs and livestock and prompt treatment after symptoms in humans are all valid ways to reduce the replenishing of pathogen load in the environment due to the excrete of leptospira by infected hosts.

For control strategies that focus on the reduction of the pathogen shedding rate, the target set is $U = \{(3, 1), (3, 2)\}$. Thus, the target matrix is:

$$\mathbf{K}_U = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{c_1}{\mu_1 + \gamma_1} & \frac{c_2}{\mu_2 + \gamma_2} & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Similar to the case (A), we have

$$\rho(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_U) < 1 \iff \max\{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2\} < 1. \quad (8)$$

Moreover, given that

$$(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_U)^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} & 0 & \frac{\beta_{1p} N_1^*}{\mu_p(1 - \mathcal{R}_1)} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2} & \frac{\beta_{2p} N_2^*}{\mu_p(1 - \mathcal{R}_2)} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

as long as the condition (8) is fulfilled the target reproduction number for the set U is given by

$$\mathcal{T}_U = \frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2}, \quad (9)$$

which coincides with the formula (7). This reflects the fact that there is a reciprocal feedback between strategies (A) and (B) i.e. when the shedding rate is reduced, the risk of getting infected through contact with a contaminated environment also decreases and vice versa.

(C) *Combination of approaches (A) and (B)*. In this case the target set is $W = \{(1, 3), (2, 3), (3, 1), (3, 2)\}$. Therefore, the condition $\rho(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_W) < 1$ is equivalent to $\max\{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2\} < 1$.

The characteristic polynomial of the matrix $\mathbf{K}_W \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_W)^{-1}$ is

$$P(\lambda) = -\lambda^3 + \left(\frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2} \right) \lambda.$$

Therefore, when it is well defined, the target reproduction number is given by

$$\mathcal{T}_W = \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2}}. \quad (10)$$

From the formulas for \mathcal{T}_S , \mathcal{T}_U and \mathcal{T}_W it is easy to note that

$$1 < \mathcal{T}_W < \mathcal{T}_S = \mathcal{T}_U, \quad \mathcal{T}_S = \mathcal{T}_U < \mathcal{T}_W < 1, \quad \text{or} \quad \mathcal{T}_S = \mathcal{T}_U = \mathcal{T}_W = 1$$

which is not surprising since the intervention strategy defined by the set W is stronger than the ones defined by S and U (Shuai et al., 2013).

2.2 Numerical simulations

In this section, we explore numerically model (1). We retrieved some parameters from the literature (Baca-Carrasco et al., 2015; Holt et al., 2006; Leirs et al., 1997) and we gathered them in Table 1.

In compartmental epidemic models, a classical procedure to reduce disease spread is to choose a feasible set of model parameters

$$\theta = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n\}$$

and determine how these parameters should be changed to prevent an epidemic. In our context, this procedure let us to define the target set S as the set of indices

$$S = \{(i_1, j_1), \dots, (i_m, j_m)\},$$

with the property that if $(i, j) \in S$ then the entry k_{ij} of \mathbf{K} depends at least on one of the parameters in θ . On the other hand, if $(i, j) \notin S$ then k_{ij} is independent of the parameters in θ .

If a proportion bigger than $1 - 1/\mathcal{T}_S$ of the entries S in \mathbf{K} can be reduced, then the disease can be eradicated. In particular, replacing the entry k_{ij} in \mathbf{K} by k_{ij}/\mathcal{T}_S whenever $(i, j) \in S$, a controlled next-generation matrix \mathbf{K}_c is formulated

$$[\mathbf{K}_c]_{ij} = \begin{cases} k_{ij}/\mathcal{T}_S, & \text{if } (i, j) \in S \\ k_{ij}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Parameter	Range	Units
A_1	[6.0, 29.0]	person day ⁻¹
β_{11}	[1×10^{-3} , 5×10^{-2}]	day ⁻¹
β_{1p}	[3×10^{-3} , 6×10^{-3}]	leptospires ⁻¹ day ⁻¹
μ_1	[1/29200, 1/14600]	day ⁻¹
γ_1	[1/20, 1/7]	day ⁻¹
ν_1	[1/365, 1/10]	day ⁻¹
A_2	[0.5, 4.0]	animal day ⁻¹
β_{22}	[1×10^{-3} , 7×10^{-2}]	day ⁻¹
β_{2p}	[1×10^{-3} , 9×10^{-3}]	leptospires ⁻¹ day ⁻¹
μ_2	[1/10950, 1/365]	day ⁻¹
γ_2	[1/30, 1/10]	day ⁻¹
ν_2	[1/90, 1/30]	day ⁻¹
c_1	[8.4×10^{-8} , 2.1×10^{-7}]	leptospires person ⁻¹ day ⁻¹
c_2	[2×10^{-4} , 2×10^{-2}]	leptospires animal ⁻¹ day ⁻¹
μ_p	[1/180, 1/4]	day ⁻¹

Table 1: Estimation of parameters for the two-group model of leptospiral infection in humans and animals (1).

and $\rho(\mathbf{K}_c) = 1$ (Shuai et al., 2013). Therefore, the goal is to change the set of parameters θ in such a way that \mathbf{K} is transformed into \mathbf{K}_c .

Let us now analyze the case in which the intervention targets both the shedding rates c_i and the transmission rates via the environment β_{ip} , with $i = 1, 2$. Thus,

$$\theta = \{c_1, c_2, \beta_{1p}, \beta_{2p}\} \quad (11)$$

Model parameters (11) involve the set of indices $W = \{(1, 3), (2, 3), (3, 1), (3, 2)\}$. Therefore, according to (C) above, the target reproduction number is

$$\mathcal{T}_W = \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2}}.$$

In order to illustrate the dynamics of the model, we check numerically the prevalence on humans and animals as functions of time. We will fix the parameters with the following baseline values (see Table 1) consistent with the literature: $A_1 = 20$, $\beta_{11} = 0.02$, $\beta_{1p} = 0.005$, $\mu_1 = 1/25550$, $\gamma_1 = 1/15$, $\nu_1 = 1/60$, $A_2 = 3$, $\beta_{22} = 0.01$, $\beta_{2p} = 0.005$, $\mu_2 = 1/3650$, $\gamma_2 = 1/20$, $\nu_2 = 1/70$, $c_1 = 1 \times 10^{-7}$, $c_2 = 1 \times 10^{-4}$, $\mu_p = 1/100$.

Fig. 2: Prevalence as function of time of humans I_1 (a) and animals I_2 (b), without control (solid curves) and with control (dashed curves). The parameters are as described in the text. In the case with control, we replaced the parameters in the set (11), that is, c_1 , c_2 , β_{1p} and β_{2p} by the controlled parameters $\tilde{c}_1 = c_1/\mathcal{T}_W$, $\tilde{c}_2 = c_2/\mathcal{T}_W$, $\tilde{\beta}_{1p} = \beta_{1p}/\mathcal{T}_W$ and $\tilde{\beta}_{2p} = \beta_{2p}/\mathcal{T}_W$, respectively.

For the baseline parameters values, the local reproduction numbers take the values $\mathcal{R}_1 = 0.2998$, $\mathcal{R}_2 = 0.1989$, $\mathcal{R}_{1p} = 0.6188$, and $\mathcal{R}_{2p} = 3.3001$. Correspondingly, $\mathcal{T}_W = 3.7610$. The target reproduction number is larger \mathcal{T}_W than 1 and thus $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$ (in fact $\mathcal{R}_0 = 3.4603$). Therefore the disease-free equilibrium is unstable (see Theorem 1 below) and we need to apply the intervention. The eradication of the disease is achieved replacing the entry $k_{ij} \in \mathbf{K}$

with $(i, j) \in W$ by k_{ij}/\mathcal{T}_W . This transformation can be easily done dividing the parameters in (11) by \mathcal{T}_W .

The results of the simulations are shown in Fig. 2. In part (a), we plotted the prevalence in humans I_1 and in part (b) the prevalence in animals I_2 . For both (a) and (b) the prevalence as function of time is represented by solid curves in the case without control and represented by dashed curves in the case with control i.e. when $k_{ij} \in \mathbf{K}$ with $(i, j) \in W$ is replaced by k_{ij}/\mathcal{T}_W . As we can see in Fig. 2, in the case without control the disease is endemic in the population; however, applying the intervention the prevalence converges to zero and the epidemic is prevented.

3 General Models

In the work that follows, we further explore the ideas of the previous section in compartmental models with n host groups sharing a common source of infection besides a possible infection among members of the same group.

This kind of dynamics can be observed in a wide variety of scenarios. For example, it may model a shopping center that is visited by people from different locations. It also can be applied to sexually transmitted diseases with a core group capable of infecting all other groups, but with no direct transmission among the rest of the groups as illustrated in (Edwards et al., 2010).

3.1 A model for environmentally-driven infectious diseases with n host types.

In accordance with the World Health Organization (WHO) more than 20% of the burden of global diseases can be attributed to environmental factors (Prüss-Üstün and Corvalán, 2006). Particularly, in developing countries, because of the lack of health-care access, environmental conditions play an important role in the possible outbreak of a significant number of diseases. Naturally, this is the case for infections caused by pathogens with the ability to survive in the environment (soil, water, air, food, contact surfaces, etc). Therefore, when attacking infections with free-living pathogens in the environment it is vital to minimize exposure to environmental risk factors such as unsafe drinking water, air pollution, and other sanitation problems.

In this section, we study a model for infections caused by a pathogen that can survive in the environment for a period of time. Examples of infections of this kind are leptospirosis, cholera, schistosomiasis, hepatitis A, toxoplasmosis among many others. For this group of infectious, the presence of pathogen in the environment is replenished by infectious host that excrete the pathogen into the environment, see (Garira et al., 2014; Bani-Yaghoub et al., 2012; Tien and Earn, 2010) and the references therein.

The model presented here is a classical *SIRS* model that generalizes system (1) to include n different host types since given the broad scope of environmental factors it is usual that these diseases affect a large range of individuals that

can be subdivided according to different criteria e.g. spatial location, high-risk and low-risk groups, age, specie, among others. We also included an equation for the pathogen dynamics.

The construction of our model rest on the following assumptions:

- (i) The total population for each host type is divided into susceptible, infectious, and recovered individuals, denoted S_i , I_i and R_i , respectively. Hence, the total population size for each type at time t is $N_i(t) = S_i(t) + I_i(t) + R_i(t)$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Individuals enter to the population as susceptible at a constant rate Λ_i and die at a per capita rate μ_i , $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.
- (ii) We assume that there is direct transmission within individuals of the same host type and indirect transmission through contact with a contaminated environment but there are no contacts among the different host types. Host-to-host transmission is modeled with standard incidence and has transmission rate β_{ii} , $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Environment-to-host transmission is modeled with mass action incidence and has transmission rate β_{ip} , $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.
- (iii) Infected individuals of host type $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ recover at a constant rate γ_i proportional to the size their class and the loss of immunity occurs at an average time of $1/\nu_i$.
- (iv) Infected hosts excrete pathogen into the environment at a rate c_i , $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, and μ_p is the pathogen clearance rate from the environment.

These assumptions give the following system of differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{S}_i &= \Lambda_i - (\beta_{ii}I_i/N_i + \beta_{ip}P)S_i - \mu_i S_i + \nu_i R_i, \\
 \dot{I}_i &= (\beta_{ii}I_i/N_i + \beta_{ip}P)S_i - (\mu_i + \gamma_i)I_i, \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \\
 \dot{R}_i &= \gamma_i I_i - (\nu_i + \mu_i)R_i, \\
 \dot{P} &= \sum_{i=1}^n c_i I_i - \mu_p P,
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where all the parameters are assumed nonnegative.

3.1.1 Global stability of the disease-free equilibrium

Until now, we have assumed that the disease can be eradicated when the target reproduction number is less than 1. However, for that to be true, we need to prove that the disease-free equilibrium is globally asymptotically stable if and only if $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$. In order to prove the global stability of the disease-free equilibrium, we will construct a suitable Lyapunov function using the methods presented in (Arino and Portet, 2015; Vargas-De-León, 2011).

To determine the disease-free equilibrium of model (12), we set the derivatives equal to zero and solve the system

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \Lambda_i - (\beta_{ii}I_i/N_i + \beta_{ip}P)S_i - \mu_i S_i + \nu_i R_i, \\ 0 &= (\beta_{ii}I_i/N_i + \beta_{ip}P)S_i - (\mu_i + \gamma_i)I_i, \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \\ 0 &= \gamma_i I_i - (\nu_i + \mu_i)R_i, \\ 0 &= \sum_{i=1}^n c_i I_i - \mu_p P, \end{aligned}$$

setting $I_i = 0$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Clearly, at the disease-free equilibrium, the number of individuals in the recovered classes and the amount of free-living pathogen in the environment are equal to zero. Therefore, model (12) has a unique disease-free equilibrium

$$E_0 = (\Lambda_1/\mu_1, 0, 0, \Lambda_2/\mu_2, 0, 0, \dots, \Lambda_n/\mu_n, 0, 0, 0).$$

Moreover, the total population size for host type i , is governed by the equation

$$\dot{N}_i = \Lambda_i - \mu_i N_i.$$

Hence, the total population size may vary in time but converges to the equilibrium $N_i^* = \Lambda_i/\mu_i$. We thus study (12) in the following feasible region

$$\Omega = \{(S_1, I_1, R_1, \dots, S_n, I_n, R_n, P) \in \mathbb{R}_+^{3n+1} : S_i + I_i + R_i \leq \Lambda_i/\mu_i, i = 1, \dots, n\}$$

which is clearly positively invariant under the flow of system (12).

The results regarding the local asymptotic stability of E_0 are consequence of Theorem 2 in (Van den Driessche and Watmough, 2002). For model (12), the matrices \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{V} such that $\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{V}$ corresponds to the linearization of the infectious subsystem of (12) are:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_{11} & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & \beta_{1p}N_1^* \\ 0 & \beta_{22} & 0 & \cdots & 0 & \beta_{2p}N_2^* \\ 0 & 0 & \beta_{33} & \cdots & 0 & \beta_{3p}N_3^* \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & \beta_{nn} & \beta_{np}N_n^* \\ c_1 & c_2 & c_3 & \cdots & c_n & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (13)$$

and

$$\mathbf{V} = \begin{pmatrix} \mu_1 + \gamma_1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_2 + \gamma_2 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & \mu_n + \gamma_n & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & \mu_p \end{pmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

The global behavior of the disease-free equilibrium is summarized in the following result.

Theorem 1 Let $\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{FV}^{-1}$ with \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{V} given by (13) and (14), respectively. If the basic reproduction number $\mathcal{R}_0 = \rho(\mathbf{K})$ satisfies $\mathcal{R}_0 \leq 1$, then the disease-free equilibrium E_0 of model (12) is globally asymptotically stable in Ω .

Proof By construction, the matrix \mathbf{F} has only nonnegative entries and the matrix \mathbf{V} is an M -matrix (Van den Driessche and Watmough, 2002). From matrix theory, we now that the spectral radius of \mathbf{FV}^{-1} and $\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{F}$ are the same, therefore $\mathcal{R}_0 = \rho(\mathbf{FV}^{-1}) = \rho(\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{F})$ (Horn and Johnson, 2013). Moreover, $(\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{F})^2$ is entry-wise positive, thus $\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{F}$ is primitive and by Perron's Theorem (Berman and Shaked-Monderer, 2012), $\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{F}$ has a positive unique left eigenvector $\mathbf{w} = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n, w_p)$ such that

$$(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n, w_p)\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{F} = \mathcal{R}_0(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n, w_p).$$

Let $\mathbf{P} = (I_1, I_2, \dots, I_n, P)^T$, $k_i = w_i/(\mu_i + \gamma_i)$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $k_p = w_p/\mu_p$. Define the function

$$L = \sum_{i=1}^n k_i I_i + k_p P.$$

Clearly, L is a radially unbounded function whose derivative along the solutions of (12) in Ω satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{L} &= \sum_{i=1}^n k_i [(\beta_{ii} I_i / N_i + \beta_{ip} P) S_i - (\mu_i + \gamma_i) I_i] + k_p \left[\sum_{i=1}^n c_i I_i - \mu_p P \right] \\ &\leq \sum_{i=1}^n k_i [(\beta_{ii} I_i + \beta_{ip} P N_i^*) - (\mu_i + \gamma_i) I_i] + k_p \left[\sum_{i=1}^n c_i I_i - \mu_p P \right] \\ &= (k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n, k_p) (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{V}) \mathbf{P}. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n, k_p) = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n, w_p) \mathbf{V}^{-1}$$

we obtain

$$\dot{L} \leq \mathbf{w}(\mathbf{V}^{-1}\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{I})\mathbf{P} = (\mathcal{R}_0 - 1)\mathbf{w}\mathbf{P}.$$

Clearly, if $\mathcal{R}_0 \leq 1$ then $\dot{L} \leq 0$. Hence, L is a Lyapunov function for model (12). Moreover, since for all i the constants k_i are positive, $\dot{L} = 0$ implies that \mathbf{P} is equal to the zero vector. Using $I_i = 0$ and $P = 0$, it is easy to see that $R_i \rightarrow 0$ and $S_i \rightarrow \Lambda_i/\mu_i$. Therefore, if $\mathcal{R}_0 \leq 1$ it follows from LaSalle's invariance principle (La Salle et al., 1962), that every solution of the equations in the model (12), with initial condition in Ω , approaches E_0 as $t \rightarrow \infty$. \square

3.1.2 Control strategies

When the control strategy is based on reducing the pathogen shedding by infectious hosts and minimizing exposure to environmental risk factors, we have the following result that generalizes the result obtained in section 2.1 (C).

Theorem 2 Consider the epidemiological model (12) and define the target set as $W = \{(1, n+1), (2, n+1), \dots, (n, n+1), (n+1, 1), (n+1, 2), \dots, (n+1, n)\}$. Provided that the condition

$$\max\{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2, \dots, \mathcal{R}_n\} < 1$$

is satisfied, the target reproduction number \mathcal{T}_W is given by

$$\mathcal{T}_W = \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2} + \dots + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{np}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_n}}, \quad (15)$$

where

$$\mathcal{R}_i = \frac{\beta_{ii}}{\mu_i + \gamma_i} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{R}_{ip} = \sqrt{\frac{c_i \beta_{ip} N_i^*}{\mu_p (\mu_i + \gamma_i)}}.$$

Proof The $(n+1) \times (n+1)$ next-generation matrix \mathbf{K} for model (12) is given by

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{R}_1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & \frac{\beta_{1p} N_1^*}{\mu_p} \\ 0 & \mathcal{R}_2 & 0 & \dots & 0 & \frac{\beta_{2p} N_2^*}{\mu_p} \\ 0 & 0 & \mathcal{R}_3 & \dots & 0 & \frac{\beta_{3p} N_3^*}{\mu_p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \mathcal{R}_n & \frac{\beta_{np} N_n^*}{\mu_p} \\ \frac{c_1}{\mu_1 + \gamma_1} & \frac{c_2}{\mu_2 + \gamma_2} & \frac{c_3}{\mu_3 + \gamma_3} & \dots & \frac{c_n}{\mu_n + \gamma_n} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

which is irreducible. Since the matrix $(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_W)$ is the diagonal matrix $\text{diag}(\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2, \dots, \mathcal{R}_n, 0)$ it is clear that

$$\rho(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_W) < 1 \iff \max\{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2, \dots, \mathcal{R}_n\} < 1.$$

Furthermore, using induction it can be proved that the characteristic polynomial of the matrix $\mathbf{K}_W \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_W)^{-1}$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & \frac{\beta_{1p} N_1^*}{\mu_p} \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & \frac{\beta_{2p} N_2^*}{\mu_p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & \frac{\beta_{np} N_n^*}{\mu_p} \\ \frac{c_1/(\mu_1 + \gamma_1)}{(1 - \mathcal{R}_1)} & \frac{c_2/(\mu_2 + \gamma_2)}{(1 - \mathcal{R}_2)} & \cdots & \frac{c_n/(\mu_n + \gamma_n)}{(1 - \mathcal{R}_n)} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

is given by

$$P(\lambda) = (-1)^{n+1} \lambda^{n+1} + (-1)^n \left(\frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} + \cdots + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{np}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_n} \right) \lambda^{n-1}. \quad (17)$$

By definition, the value of the target reproduction number \mathcal{T}_W is equal to the root of largest modulus of the polynomial (17) which it is given by the right-hand side of (15). \square

Several properties make the target reproduction number such a useful quantity. First, it shares the threshold property of the basic reproduction number ($\mathcal{T}_W < 1$ if and only if $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$; and $\mathcal{T}_W = 1$ if and only if $\mathcal{R}_0 = 1$). Second, if the values of the entries W in the next-generation matrix \mathbf{K} are reduced by a proportion more than $1 - 1/\mathcal{T}_W$, then the disease will die out. The only requirements for this to be true is that $\rho(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_W) < 1$ and the next-generation matrix \mathbf{K} to be irreducible.

As a decision maker, one might be concerned about how to lower the value of the target reproduction number below 1. In this case, it is important to know how sensitive is \mathcal{T}_W to the values of the reproduction numbers associated to the environment-to-host and host-to-host transmission cycles to decide on which of the two to invest. This can be done, for instance, using the partial derivatives of \mathcal{T}_W . For example, from (15) it is easy to prove that,

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{T}_W}{\partial \mathcal{R}_i} \leq \frac{\partial \mathcal{T}_W}{\partial \mathcal{R}_{ip}} \iff \frac{\mathcal{R}_{ip}}{2(1 - \mathcal{R}_i)} \leq 1, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

Therefore, \mathcal{T}_W is more sensitive to the reproduction number \mathcal{R}_{ip} than to \mathcal{R}_i if and only if $\mathcal{R}_{ip} \leq 2(1 - \mathcal{R}_i)$, see Fig. 3. If other things being equal, this simple analysis tells us if it is more convenient to reduce \mathcal{R}_i or \mathcal{R}_{ip} when controlling the i^{th} host type. However, this sensitivity is local since it does not take into account the simultaneous variation of input parameters.

The following theorem establishes the generalization of the result obtained for approach (A) in section 2.1.

Fig. 3: Region (blue) in which the target reproduction number \mathcal{T}_W is more sensitive to the reproduction number associated to the environment-to-host transmission \mathcal{R}_{ip} than to the reproduction number of the host-to-host transmission \mathcal{R}_i .

Theorem 3 Consider the epidemiological model (12) and define the target set as $S = \{(1, n + 1), (2, n + 1), \dots, (n, n + 1)\}$. Provided that the condition

$$\max\{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2, \dots, \mathcal{R}_n\} < 1 \quad (18)$$

is satisfied, the target reproduction number \mathcal{T}_S is given by

$$\mathcal{T}_S = \frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2} + \dots + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{np}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_n}. \quad (19)$$

Proof By definition, the target matrix \mathbf{K}_S is given by

$$\mathbf{K}_S = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & \frac{\beta_{1p}N_1^*}{\mu_p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & \frac{\beta_{np}N_n^*}{\mu_p} \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

Consequently, the matrix $\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_S$ is a triangular matrix with $\mathcal{R}_1, \dots, \mathcal{R}_n$ and 0 in its diagonal, hence $\rho(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_S) < 1$ is equivalent to condition (18). The

product $\mathbf{K}_S \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_S)^{-1}$ is given by the following matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} & \frac{c_2 \beta_{1p} N_1^*}{\mu_p(\mu_2 + \gamma_2)(1 - \mathcal{R}_2)} & \frac{c_3 \beta_{1p} N_1^*}{\mu_p(\mu_3 + \gamma_3)(1 - \mathcal{R}_3)} & \dots & \frac{c_n \beta_{1p} N_1^*}{\mu_p(\mu_n + \gamma_n)(1 - \mathcal{R}_n)} & \frac{\beta_{1p} N_1^*}{\mu_p} \\ \frac{c_1 \beta_{2p} N_2^*}{\mu_p(\mu_1 + \gamma_1)(1 - \mathcal{R}_1)} & \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2} & \frac{c_3 \beta_{2p} N_2^*}{\mu_p(\mu_3 + \gamma_3)(1 - \mathcal{R}_3)} & \dots & \frac{c_n \beta_{2p} N_2^*}{\mu_p(\mu_n + \gamma_n)(1 - \mathcal{R}_n)} & \frac{\beta_{2p} N_2^*}{\mu_p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{c_1 \beta_{np} N_n^*}{\mu_p(\mu_1 + \gamma_1)(1 - \mathcal{R}_1)} & \frac{c_2 \beta_{np} N_n^*}{\mu_p(\mu_2 + \gamma_2)(1 - \mathcal{R}_2)} & \frac{c_3 \beta_{np} N_n^*}{\mu_p(\mu_3 + \gamma_3)(1 - \mathcal{R}_3)} & \dots & \frac{\mathcal{R}_{np}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_n} & \frac{\beta_{np} N_n^*}{\mu_p} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

It is easy to see that $\text{rank}(\mathbf{K}_S \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_S)^{-1}) = 1$ since all the columns of $\mathbf{K}_S \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_S)^{-1}$ are scalar multiples of its first column. Hence, $\mathbf{K}_S \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_S)^{-1}$ only has a nonzero eigenvalue, which implies

$$\rho(\mathbf{K}_S \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_S)^{-1}) = \frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2} + \dots + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{np}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_n}$$

because the trace of a matrix is equal to the sum of its eigenvalues. \square

In cases when the control strategy focuses on reducing the shedding rate of infectious hosts, we have the following result.

Theorem 4 Consider the epidemiological model (12) and define the target set as $U = \{(n+1, 1), (n+1, 2), \dots, (n+1, n)\}$. Provided that the condition

$$\max\{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2, \dots, \mathcal{R}_n\} < 1 \quad (21)$$

is satisfied, the target reproduction number \mathcal{T}_U is given by

$$\mathcal{T}_U = \frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2} + \dots + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{np}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_n}. \quad (22)$$

Proof It is straightforward to see that

$$\rho(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_U) < 1 \iff \max\{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2, \dots, \mathcal{R}_n\} < 1.$$

Moreover, the matrix $\mathbf{K}_U \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_U)^{-1}$ is a lower triangular matrix with 0's in the first n elements of its diagonal and

$$\frac{\mathcal{R}_{1p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_1} + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2p}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_2} + \dots + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{np}^2}{1 - \mathcal{R}_n}$$

as the last element of its diagonal. \square

One of the advantages of using the target reproduction number is making a big problem smaller. Instead of struggling with the complete and probably very complex \mathcal{R}_0 , one can handle a much smaller amount of information: some of the entries of the next-generation matrix.

Therefore, although \mathcal{T}_S and \mathcal{T}_U have the same value. In real life, one of the two strategies may have advantages over the other one. For instance, assuming

that we want to reduce the value of the entries U of the next-generation matrix \mathbf{K} (16) by a proportion more than $1 - 1/\mathcal{T}_U$, then we have to reduce the pathogen shedding rate or increase the recovery rate in each host class. But, if the objective is to reduce the entries S in \mathbf{K} ; increasing the pathogen clearance rate μ_p reduces all of these entries at the same time. This could be a practical advantage of the last strategy over the first one.

How multiple transmission routes affect the spread of many environmentally-driven diseases is not well-understood (Tien and Earn, 2010). Nevertheless, the host-to-host transmission pathway has been traditionally considered as the predominant cause of disease spread (Bani-Yaghoub et al., 2012). For model (12), infectious individuals can transmit the infection both through direct contact with a susceptible person and also by pathogen shedding into the environment. One of the basic aims of this work is to explore the role of the host-environment-host indirect transmission pathway. Therefore, control strategies (A), (B) and (C) essentially focus on controlling environmental factors.

3.2 A metapopulation model with a central patch

In this section, we consider a metapopulation model with $n+1$ patches that can be thought of as cities, countries, or other geographically autonomous regions with the particularity that one of them is the gravity center that connects the other ones.

We propose a compartmental *SIRS* model for each patch. For the central patch, we are going to denote the total population at time t by $N_c(t)$, whereas $S_c(t)$, $I_c(t)$ and $R_c(t)$ give the number of susceptible, infectious and recovered individuals at time t , respectively. For the remaining n patches the classes are denoted by $S_i(t)$, $I_i(t)$ and $R_i(t)$ with $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. So the total population at time t in patch i is $N_i(t) = S_i(t) + I_i(t) + R_i(t)$ for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n, c\} := J$.

Concerning movement, we assume that the members of the region $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ make short-term visits to the central region and return to the home patch, while individuals in the central patch can travel to all the remaining patches and then get back home. When infectious individuals are visiting another region they can infect the susceptible individuals of that region. Likewise, the susceptible ones that travel can be infected by infectious ones of the visited region.

For the sake of clarity, the incidence will be governed by the mass action law and we also assume that all individuals are born susceptibles. The metapopulation *SIRS* model takes the following form

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{S}_i &= \Lambda_i - (\beta_{ii}I_i + \beta_{ic}I_c)S_i - \mu_i S_i + \nu_i R_i, \\ \dot{I}_i &= (\beta_{ii}I_i + \beta_{ic}I_c)S_i - (\mu_i + \gamma_i)I_i, \\ \dot{R}_i &= \gamma_i I_i - (\nu_i + \mu_i)R_i,\end{aligned}\tag{23}$$

for patches $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. While for the central patch,

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{S}_c &= \Lambda_c - \beta_{cc}S_cI_c - \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{ci}S_cI_i - \mu_cS_c + \nu_cR_c, \\ \dot{I}_c &= \beta_{cc}S_cI_c + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{ci}S_cI_i - (\mu_c + \gamma_c)I_c, \\ \dot{R}_c &= \gamma_cI_c - (\nu_c + \mu_c)R_c.\end{aligned}\tag{24}$$

Here, Λ_i are recruitment rates, β_{ij} are the transmission rates of infectious individuals from patch j to susceptible individuals in patch i . The mortality rates are denoted by μ_i and γ_i represent recovery rates. The average duration of the immune period for individuals in patch $i \in J$ is $1/\nu_i$. The graph associated to the dynamics of the infection process is shown in Fig. 4.

For a metapopulation epidemic model patches should be connected through migration. This movement of individuals from one area to another can be short-term or long-term. The long-term movement appears when people move to another area and not necessarily come back to the home patch. Arino and Portet (Arino and Portet, 2015) studied long-term movement in a metapopulation model whose infection process follows the same structure than system (23)-(24). Besides the type of movement, the difference between system (23)-(24) and Arino's model is that we assumed a *SIRS* structure while in (Arino and Portet, 2015) the authors omitted the possible loss of immunity of the individuals.

To see that solutions of the model (23)-(24) with nonnegative initial conditions remain nonnegative consider when at least one of the phase space variables x_i is equal to zero. Direct computation gives that if $x_i = 0$, then $\dot{x}_i \geq 0$ where $x \in \{S, I, R\}$ and $i \in J$. Thus, solutions cannot become negative for future times. The total population size of the complete system $N = \sum_{i \in J} N_i$ satisfies

$$\dot{N} \leq \Lambda - \mu N, \quad \text{with} \quad \Lambda = \sum_{i \in J} \Lambda_i, \quad \mu = \min_{i \in J} \{\mu_i\},$$

therefore

$$\limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} N(t) \leq \Lambda/\mu.$$

It follows that solutions of (23)-(24) are bounded. Moreover, for all the patches, the total population size of the patch converges to $N_i^* = \Lambda_i/\mu_i$ with $i \in J$. Then, the region

$$\Gamma = \{(S_1, I_1, R_1, \dots, S_c, I_c, R_c) \in \mathbb{R}_+^{3n+3} : S_i + I_i + R_i \leq \Lambda_i/\mu_i, i \in J\}$$

is positively invariant under the flow of (23)-(24).

The disease-free equilibrium \tilde{E} obtained by solving for S_i and R_i after setting $I_i = 0$, takes the values $S_i^* = N_i^*$ and $R_i^* = 0$ for $i \in J$. Thus,

$$\tilde{E} = (N_1^*, 0, 0, \dots, N_n^*, 0, 0, N_c^*, 0, 0)\tag{25}$$

Fig. 4: Topological structure of the infection process for model (23)-(24). The reproduction numbers \mathcal{R}_i correspond to the isolated dynamics of patch $i \in J$, while the reproduction numbers \mathcal{R}_{ic} are associated with the commuting between the central patch and patch i , $1 \leq i \leq n$.

is the unique disease-free equilibrium of model (23)-(24). As in the proof of Theorem 1, constructing a suitable Lyapunov function we can prove the following result.

Theorem 5 *Let \mathbf{K} be the next-generation matrix for model (23)-(24) and $\mathcal{R}_0 = \rho(\mathbf{K})$. If the basic reproduction number satisfies $\mathcal{R}_0 \leq 1$, then the disease-free equilibrium \tilde{E} of the metapopulation model (23)-(24) is globally asymptotically stable in Γ .*

Since it has been proved the importance of the mobility component in the persistence of diseases in metapopulation models (Arino and Van den Driessche, 2003) our control strategy shall focus on the interactions between patches rather than the local dynamics of each patch.

Theorem 6 *Provided that the condition*

$$\max\{\mathcal{R}_1, \dots, \mathcal{R}_n, \mathcal{R}_c\} < 1 \quad (26)$$

is fulfilled, the target reproduction number \mathcal{T}_Z for system (23)-(24) where the target set is defined as $Z = \{(1, n+1), (2, n+1), \dots, (n, n+1), (n+1, 1), (n+1, 2), \dots, (n+1, n)\}$ is given by

$$\mathcal{T}_Z = \sqrt{\frac{1}{(1-\mathcal{R}_c)} \left(\frac{\mathcal{R}_{1c}^2}{1-\mathcal{R}_1} + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{2c}^2}{1-\mathcal{R}_2} + \dots + \frac{\mathcal{R}_{nc}^2}{1-\mathcal{R}_n} \right)}, \quad (27)$$

where

$$\mathcal{R}_i = \frac{\beta_{ii}N_i^*}{\mu_i + \gamma_i}, \quad i \in J \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{R}_{ic} = \sqrt{\frac{\beta_{ic}\beta_{ci}N_i^*N_c^*}{(\mu_i + \gamma_i)(\mu_c + \gamma_c)}}, \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$$

are the basic reproduction numbers of the within-patch transmission and the infectious caused by the commuting between the $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ patches and the central patch, respectively (see Fig. 4).

The proof follows the same idea that Theorem 3.1 and it is therefore omitted.

Observe that in the calculated target reproduction number (27), in the denominator arise expressions of the form $1 - \mathcal{R}_i$, $i \in J$. Thus, in a limit sense, the value of \mathcal{T}_Z goes to infinity as \mathcal{R}_i tend to 1. This seems to contradict the fact that

$$\mathcal{T}_Z < 1 \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{R}_0 < 1, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{T}_Z = 1 \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{R}_0 = 1 \quad (28)$$

when the target reproduction number is well defined. However, this is not a discrepancy since \mathcal{R}_i , $i \in J$, are local reproduction numbers associated to sub-models and relation (28) only applies for the basic reproduction number of the complete model.

We also want to emphasize that the conceptual idea of the design of control strategies from the topological structure of the infection process is applicable to a broad range of models beyond those where the heterogeneity is spatial. For example, infectious process related to vector-borne diseases that affect multiple host species have an analogous structure that the one presented in Fig. 4, with the difference that the reproduction numbers associated to the within-species transmission are zero. In the above case, the vector has the function of transmitting the infection to the different species so it works as the common source of infection.

4 Discussion

In recent years, the fast development of the field of mathematical epidemiology has included a wide range of multigroup mathematical models that consider host heterogeneities. However, much remains to be understood about how such heterogeneities and the topological structure of the infection process affect the spread of infectious diseases and our capacity to control them.

Even though \mathcal{R}_0 is a linear measure of the strength of the infection, under the homogeneous mixing assumption, it aptly determines the control effort needed to eradicate an infection (Roberts and Heesterbeek, 2003) which is one of the fundamental tasks in the mathematical modeling of infectious diseases. However, for a large number of diseases there are multiple factors such as physiological, geographical or even economic conditions that affect the trend of the infection and therefore the homogeneous mixing assumption is no longer valid. This might make it necessary to consider different host types where each group guarantees homogeneous mixing. Once having several host types, the

basic reproduction number often appears as complex combinations of parameters that make any analysis difficult. In these cases, \mathcal{R}_0 does not improve our understanding of how efforts should be focused to eliminate the epidemic (Olmos et al., 2015).

In this paper, we bring forward some techniques to reduce the value of \mathcal{R}_0 for multigroup models even without explicitly knowing its expression. Given the original model, we studied some subsystems and computed their basic reproduction numbers. These basic reproduction numbers allowed us to express the target reproduction number in a more treatable way for concrete public health interventions. In other words, our methodology focuses on preventing outbreaks at the global level by means of controlling the local dynamics of the infection process.

We started by applying these methods to a two-species model for leptospirosis. Three control policies were studied, all of them focusing on the indirect transmission caused by the interaction between hosts and the free-living leptospira in the environment. In particular, by comparing the strategy that minimizes exposures to environmental risk factors with the one that reduces the pathogen shedding rate, we found that both target reproduction numbers are equal. Biologically, this means that both processes lead to the same outcome. Therefore, one can select the strategy that is most feasible according to the local conditions. The combination of the above strategies brings a stronger strategy because for endemic cases $1 < \mathcal{T}_W < \mathcal{T}_S = \mathcal{T}_U$ and therefore $1 - 1/\mathcal{T}_W < 1 - 1/\mathcal{T}_S$. Yet, none of these strategies is good enough to control the infection when the direct transmission cycle is endemic.

In order to study infections caused by pathogens with the ability to survive in the environment, we proposed a generalization of the previous model, namely the n -groups compartmental model (12). The model includes two potential routes of transmission: host-to-host and environment-to-host transmission. Traditionally, control strategies have been focused on the host-to-host transmission pathway. Nevertheless, the relative importance of the indirect infections caused via contact with a contaminated environment is uncertain (Holt et al., 2006; Bani-Yaghoub et al., 2012; Tien and Earn, 2010). Therefore, we analyzed control strategies that center on the environment-to-host and computed the target reproduction number in each case to quantify the control effort needed to eradicate the infection.

We also studied the spread of an infection among discrete geographical regions with a core region. Even though the connection of the regions is by way of short-term movement, it still allows infectious individuals to transmit the pathogen to susceptible individuals of a different region. Theorem 6 implies that if the disease can persist even in one patch we cannot eradicate the epidemic by just controlling the movement between patches in the metapopulation model (23)-(24). In fact, we also notice that the infection can persist in the population even if all the basic reproduction numbers for the transmission within patches are less than one.

Another important observation is that the topological structure of the infection process of model (12) is a particular case of the infection cycle that

follows the metapopulation model (23)-(24). The difference is that the common source of infection in model (12) (namely the free-living pathogen) does not have the ability to produce within-group infections. On the other hand, the central group of the metapopulation model can produce within-group infections with a reproduction number \mathcal{R}_c . Also note that in qualitative terms, the strategy that aims to reduce the pathogen shedding by infectious hosts and minimize exposure to environmental risk factors in model (12), is equivalent to the strategy that focuses on reducing the infections caused by travel between patches in the metapopulation model. This explains the similarity in the target reproduction numbers (15) and (27), and lead us to remark that there is a connection among the cycles of infection, the basic reproduction number and the target reproduction number. These results illustrate that understanding the topological structure of the infection process and partitioning it in simple cycles is useful to design and evaluate control strategies.

The focus of this work has been compartmental *SIRS* models composed of n host groups with a common source of infection that fits the dynamics of a broad range of infectious diseases. Currently, we are working on extending the above ideas to more complex processes of infection beyond the star network topology.

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References

- Adler, B. and de la Peña Moctezuma, A. (2010). Leptospira and leptospirosis. *Veterinary microbiology*, 140(3):287–296.
- Arino, J. and Portet, S. (2015). Epidemiological implications of mobility between a large urban centre and smaller satellite cities. *Journal of mathematical biology*, 71(5):1243–1265.
- Arino, J. and Van den Driessche, P. (2003). A multi-city epidemic model. *Mathematical Population Studies*, 10(3):175–193.
- Baca-Carrasco, D., Olmos, D., and Barradas, I. (2015). A mathematical model for human and animal leptospirosis. *Journal of Biological Systems*, 23(supp01):S55–S65.
- Baca-Carrasco, D. and Velasco-Hernández, J. X. (2016). Sex, mosquitoes and epidemics: An evaluation of zika disease dynamics. *Bulletin of Mathematical Biology*, 78(11):2228–2242.
- Bani-Yaghoub, M., Gautam, R., Shuai, Z., van den Driessche, P., and Ivanek, R. (2012). Reproduction numbers for infections with free-living pathogens growing in the environment. *Journal of biological dynamics*, 6(2):923–940.
- Berman, A. and Shaked-Monderer, N. (2012). Non-negative matrices and digraphs. In *Computational Complexity*, pages 2082–2095. Springer.

- Chen, M. I., Ghani, A. C., and Edmunds, W. J. (2009). A metapopulation modelling framework for gonorrhoea and other sexually transmitted infections in heterosexual populations. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, 6(38):775–791.
- Edwards, R., Kim, S., and van den Driessche, P. (2010). A multigroup model for a heterosexually transmitted disease. *Mathematical biosciences*, 224(2):87–94.
- Evangelista, K. V. and Coburn, J. (2010). Leptospira as an emerging pathogen: a review of its biology, pathogenesis and host immune responses. *Future microbiology*, 5(9):1413–1425.
- Ganoza, C. A., Matthias, M. A., Collins-Richards, D., Brouwer, K. C., Cunningham, C. B., Segura, E. R., Gilman, R. H., Gotuzzo, E., and Vinetz, J. M. (2006). Determining risk for severe leptospirosis by molecular analysis of environmental surface waters for pathogenic leptospira. *PLoS medicine*, 3(8):e308.
- Garira, W., Mathebula, D., and Netshikweta, R. (2014). A mathematical modelling framework for linked within-host and between-host dynamics for infections with free-living pathogens in the environment. *Mathematical biosciences*, 256:58–78.
- Heesterbeek, J. A. P. (2002). A brief history of r_0 and a recipe for its calculation. *Acta biotheoretica*, 50(3):189–204.
- Holt, J., Davis, S., and Leirs, H. (2006). A model of leptospirosis infection in an african rodent to determine risk to humans: seasonal fluctuations and the impact of rodent control. *Acta tropica*, 99(2):218–225.
- Horn, R. A. and Johnson, C. R. (2013). Matrix analysis, 2nd.
- Keeling, M., Tildesley, M., House, T., and Danon, L. (2013). The mathematics of vaccination. *Mathematics Today*, 49:40–43.
- Knipf, D. (2016). A new approach for designing disease intervention strategies in metapopulation models. *Journal of biological dynamics*, 10(1):71–94.
- Ko, A. I., Reis, M. G., Dourado, C. M. R., Johnson, W. D., Riley, L. W., Group, S. L. S., et al. (1999). Urban epidemic of severe leptospirosis in brazil. *The Lancet*, 354(9181):820–825.
- La Salle, J., Lefschetz, S., and Alverson, R. (1962). Stability by liapunov’s direct method with applications. *Physics Today*, 15:59.
- Leirs, H., Stenseth, N. C., Nichols, J. D., Hines, J. E., Verhagen, R., and Verheyen, W. (1997). Stochastic seasonality and nonlinear density-dependent factors regulate population size in an african rodent. *Nature*, 389(6647):176.
- Martcheva, M. (2015). *Introduction to Mathematical Epidemiology*, volume 61. Springer.
- Olmos, D., Barradas, I., and Baca-Carrasco, D. (2015). On the calculation of r_0 using submodels. *Differential Equations and Dynamical Systems*, pages 1–17.
- Prüss-Üstün, A. and Corvalán, C. (2006). Preventing disease through healthy environments. *Geneva: World Health Organization*.
- Roberts, M. and Heesterbeek, J. (2003). A new method for estimating the effort required to control an infectious disease. *Proceedings of the Royal*

- Society of London B: Biological Sciences*, 270(1522):1359–1364.
- Shuai, Z., Heesterbeek, J., and van den Driessche, P. (2013). Extending the type reproduction number to infectious disease control targeting contacts between types. *Journal of mathematical biology*, 67(5):1067–1082.
- Shuai, Z., Heesterbeek, J., and van den Driessche, P. (2015). Erratum to: Extending the type reproduction number to infectious disease control targeting contacts between types. *Journal of mathematical biology*, 71(1):255–257.
- Terpstra, W. (2003). *Human leptospirosis: guidance for diagnosis, surveillance and control*. World Health Organization.
- Tien, J. H. and Earn, D. J. (2010). Multiple transmission pathways and disease dynamics in a waterborne pathogen model. *Bulletin of mathematical biology*, 72(6):1506–1533.
- Triampo, W., Baowan, D., Tang, I., Nuttavut, N., Wong-Ekkabut, J., and Dounghawee, G. (2007). A simple deterministic model for the spread of leptospirosis in thailand. *International Journal of Biological and Medical Sciences*, 2:22–26.
- Ullmann, L. and Langoni, H. (2011). Interactions between environment, wild animals and human leptospirosis. *Journal of Venomous Animals and Toxins including Tropical Diseases*, 17(2):119–129.
- Van den Driessche, P. and Watmough, J. (2002). Reproduction numbers and sub-threshold endemic equilibria for compartmental models of disease transmission. *Mathematical biosciences*, 180(1):29–48.
- Vargas-De-León, C. (2011). On the global stability of sis, sir and sirs epidemic models with standard incidence. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 44(12):1106–1110.